

Arduino based Smart Irrigation System Design, Challenges and Solutions

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Abstract

Irrigated agriculture is essential for sustaining the global food supply. Over-irrigation may result in soil erosion and increase the likelihood of surface and groundwater contamination due to runoff and leaching, often requiring the application of additional fertilizers and chemicals. In contrast, under-irrigation can compromise crop yield and quality. Mounting economic, political, and environmental pressures have intensified the need to reduce or eliminate inefficiencies in water and energy use across both agricultural and landscape irrigation systems. Employing low-cost soil moisture sensors for irrigation scheduling has proven effective in enhancing profitability while simultaneously safeguarding environmental resources.

In this study, we describe the system that we build up in order to record resistive measures of soil matric potential and automate irrigation events. The hardware design comprises of two Watermark 200SS soil moisture sensors, a flow sensor; an Arduino edge control, LCD screen, relay module, a submersible differential pressure liquid level sensor, motorized ball valves, irrigation pumps and laboratory scale pots. The developed irrigation system features two independent irrigation zones, each monitored for soil moisture in centibar units. The water flows through an YF-B2 flowmeter and distributed to the zones using two 9V DC latching solenoid valves. Each irrigation zone has an individually defined soil moisture threshold. Once this threshold is exceeded, the system triggers the respective valve to start irrigation. However, accurate soil moisture measurement requires the water to infiltrate the soil and reach the sensor. To address this, the system implements a periodic open-close valve cycle, such as 10 seconds open followed by 20 seconds wait time, and continues this cycle until the sensor reading drops below the set threshold. The system supports both in manual and automatic operational modes.

We also address two major technical challenges and mitigation strategies that we experienced in order to aid other researchers. The first challenge was the inaccurate sensor readings. As per the manufacturer's guidance, due to their high internal resistance, conventional analog readings using Arduino were unreliable. In order to solve this challenge, we integrated the 200SS-SDI sensor adapter, which is specifically designed for Watermark sensors. Using SDI-12 protocol, the adapter offered highly stable and accurate digital readings. The other major challenge was the EMI/RFI noise. Arduino and similar development boards are inherently vulnerable to electromagnetic interference due to their low-voltage operation and lack of industrial-grade protection circuitry. To resolve this, several mitigation strategies were implemented such as optocoupler modules and Schottky diodes, shielded cables, signal wires and power lines for relays and solenoids, electrical isolation of the power supply for Arduino and sensors from the relays/valves, optimized software routines, constant monitoring of SDI-12 communication and a watchdog timer. Through these measures, system stability and measurement reliability were significantly improved.

Although Arduino is ideal for prototype development, future expansions and field use cases should leverage 12V or 24V programmable logic controllers to ensure long-term reliability and integration with other industrial automation equipment.

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